

CONDENSATION OF ALDEHYDES WITH MALONIC ACID. PART XIX. CONDENSATION OF CINNAMALDEHYDE

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The condensation of cinnamaldehyde with malonic acid and 1/6 (0.15 mol.) of pyridine give within one hour's heating on a water-bath about 96% yield of cinnamylidene-malonic acid, which is higher than what has been so far recorded. Longer heating gives a mixture of the above dibasic acid with cinnamylidene-acetic acid; prolonged heating gives the mono acid alone, but in less yield. Heating without a base or any condensing agent, a mixture of the two acids is obtained in all the experiments tried.

Hitherto the aldehydes taken up in this series were aromatic aldehydes. Cinnamaldehyde may be looked upon as an aliphatic aldehyde in the sense that the aldehyde group is no longer on the nucleus as in the previous cases, but is on a side-chain, fairly away from the ring. The double bond in the side-chain helps, however, to contact the aldehyde group with the double bond system of the ring in a longer conjugated double bond system. This aldehyde therefore presents certain peculiarities in the aldehyde-malonic acid condensation, and gives yields that are comparable with those obtained from aromatic aldehydes, like benzaldehyde. There is no doubt that the reaction is quite fast, unlike what has been observed with aliphatic aldehydes. Literature on the condensation of purely acyclic aldehydes, as well as the experience obtained in this laboratory on their condensation with malonic acid, suggest that their condensation with malonic acid is not only not very quick, as has been found in the case of the aromatic aldehydes, but that the yields are generally poor and that very often the product contains mixtures of two or more acids (like α - β and β - γ unsaturated acids), particularly when secondary amines like piperidine are used (Harding and Weizmann, *J. Chem. Soc.*, 1910, 97, 299). The succeeding paper on the condensation of malonic acid with hydrocinnamaldehyde, where this conjugation of the double bonds is non-existent and the aldehyde group is not connected with the ring in that system, will make this point clear. Cinnamaldehyde thus presents certain interesting contrasts with both aromatic and aliphatic aldehydes.

Though much work has been published on the condensation of cinnamaldehyde (Perkin, *J. Chem. Soc.*, 1877, 1, 403; Stuart, *ibid.*, 1886, 49, 365; Libermann, *Ber.*, 1895, 28, 1439; Knoevenagel, *Ber.*, 1898, 31, 2617; Döbner, *Ber.*, 1902, 35, 2137; Hinrichsen and Triepel, *Annalen*, 1904, 336, 197; Riedel *ibid.*, 1908, 361, 99; Döbner and Staudinger, *Ber.*, 1903, 36, 4322; Riiber, *Ber.*, 1904, 37, 2274) there is no observation recorded (except one from this Laboratory) of condensation in the presence of a trace of pyridine and none either on the condensation carried out in the absence of any condensing agent.

By heating cinnamaldehyde with malonic acid with pyridine-piperidine mixture under reflux for 16 hours, Dutt reported a 60% yield of the cinnamylidene-acetic acid (*J. Indian Chem. Soc.*, 1925, 1, 297). He also noted that on heating for two hours only

"the main product is cinnamylidene-malonic acid, yield nearly 70%". (*ibid.*, p. 335). Boxer and Linstead condensed the two in the presence of triethanolamine, which is not found in this laboratory to be as efficient as pyridine, and found only 10% yield of the cinnamalmalonic acid (*J. Chem. Soc.*, 1931, 740). Dalal and Dutt have condensed the two in the presence of quinoline at 80-88° for 5 hours and obtained about 76% yield of the dibasic acid (*J. Indian Chem. Soc.*, 1932, 9, 309).

Kurien and Pandya, using 0.15 mol. of pyridine for one mol. each of the aldehyde and of malonic acid and heating for only one hour on the water-bath obtained (1931) 90% yield of the cinnamylidene-malonic acid. The dibasic acid was changed to the monobasic (yield 50%) on continuing the heating for 18 hours (*J. Indian Chem. Soc.*, 1934, 11, 825)*. This suggests some other simultaneous or subsequent reaction taking place, in addition to simple decarboxylation.

The last experiment has now been repeated; it is found that under the usual conditions of the condensation and employing 0.15 mol. of pyridine, the product is a mixture of the di- and the mono-acids. But on restricting the heating to only 1 hour on a water-bath, the maximum yield of 96% of pure dibasic acid is obtained. This is quite comparable with the maximum yield obtained from benzaldehyde-malonic acid (Pandya and Miss Pandya, *Proc. Ind. Acad. Sci.*, 1941, 13A, 116). With a trace of pyridine even 12 hours' heating on a water-bath, continued to give a mixture of the two acids, though the proportion of the mono-acid to that of the dibasic acid, went on increasing as the heating time was increased. In the absence of pyridine also a mixture of the two acids, varying in the same way, was obtained, and none of the two acids came out alone under any condition of heating when no condensing agent was used. Cinnamylidene-malonic acid is a bright yellow crystalline solid, while the monocinnamylidene-acetic acid is white.

EXPERIMENTAL

Condensation in the Presence of Pyridine

(i) Cinnamaldehyde (1.32 g.), malonic acid (1.04 g.) and 0.13 c. c. of pyridine (1:1:0.15 mol.) were heated together on a water-bath for 6 hours. The reaction started immediately and the mixture changed into a homogeneous liquid in 5 minutes. There was no effervescence, but in another 15 minutes a yellow solid began to separate, and after about $\frac{1}{2}$ hour's heating the whole reaction mixture became solid. After 3 hours' heating, the yellow solid began to liquify with effervescence, leaving a clear, brown liquid. After full 6 hours' heating, the flask was allowed to cool and left overnight. A yellow-brown solid was found next morning which could all be dissolved in sodium carbonate solution. It was extracted with ether, which gave about 0.2 g. of unused cinnamaldehyde. On acidification of the aqueous solution, a yellow-brown solid was obtained, which was washed with water and dried, yield 1.65 g., m.p. 146-195°, showing that it was a mixture of the two acids. Hot benzene effected a separation into the dibasic cinnamylidene-malonic acid, which was very little soluble, and the monobasic cinnamylidene-acetic acid which dissolved easily.

*The statement printed in the paper that pyridine was 3 c.c. is a printing mistake; it should have been 0.3 c.c. K. C. P.

The former was recrystallised from alcohol and then from chloroform, m.p. 206° (cf. Stuart, *loc. cit.*, m.p. 208°). The mono-acid was recrystallised from hot benzene, then from acetic acid with a drop or so of water; the pure crystals melted at 165-66° (cf. Perkin, 165-66°, Stuart, 165°, *loc. cit.*) The mixture seemed to contain about 56% of the dibasic acid and 44% of the monobasic, the total yield being about 82% of the theoretical (or a little more, if the unused aldehyde is deducted from the aldehyde taken).

(ii) A second experiment was set up in the same way, but the heating was stopped after 3 hours in order to avoid the decarboxylation and to obtain the pure dibasic acid. The product, however, was already semi-solid, and after the removal of 0.1 g. of unused cinnamaldehyde, gave again a mixture of the two acids, but now in the proportion of 80:20, the total yield being about 88%.

(iii) *Preparation of pure Cinnamylidene-malonic Acid.*—The experiment was again repeated, but the heating was stopped after $\frac{1}{2}$ hour, when the reaction mixture had completely solidified after fusion. Unused cinnamaldehyde was recovered (0.2 g.), and the pure dibasic acid was obtained, m.p. 206-208°. After recrystallisation (alcohol) bright yellow needles melted at 207-208°, yield 1.75 g. or 94%.

(iv) The experiment was again repeated, but the heating was allowed to go on for 1 hour; this gave the maximum yield of the pure dibasic acid, 98% of theory.

(v) *Preparation of Cinnamylidene-acetic Acid.*—The experiment was repeated with the object of converting all the product into the mono-acid. With 9 hours' heating and with 0.2 g. of the aldehyde recovered unchanged, the product was a mixture containing 24% of the dibasic and 76% of the monobasic acid, total yield being 79%.

(vi) With 12 hours' heating, however, the decarboxylation was complete; the recrystallised mono-acid melted at 166-67°, the yield was only 55%, or subtracting the unchanged aldehyde recovered, 61%. As no amount of dibasic acid was recovered and yet the yield had diminished, it is presumed that some of the acid must have undergone another change, possibly dimerisation.

(vii) Cinnamylidene-malonic acid (0.43 g.) was heated in a small flask at 210-215° for about $\frac{1}{2}$ hour. Effervescence continued from the melted mass for about 15 minutes. After cooling and dissolving it in sodium carbonate solution, and after filtering off a little resinous mass, it was acidified, when a white solid, m.p. 160°, was obtained. After recrystallisation, the melting-point rose to 165-66°, and the acid was identical with cinnamylidene-acetic acid.

(viii) The same amount of the dibasic acid was heated with quinoline (0.26 g.) at 200° for 15 minutes. After the usual process of the purification a colorless solid (about 0.25 g.) came out, melting (after recrystallisation from dilute alcohol) at 137-38° (Libermann's *allo-cinnamylidene-acetic acid* melts at 138°, *loc. cit.*).

Condensation in the Absence of any Condensing Agent

(i) The same amounts of cinnamaldehyde and malonic acid were heated alone on a water-bath for 9 hours. Within 5 minutes the whole had liquified, effervescence started after about 15 minutes. A yellowish black solid was first formed but it soon disappeared. The next day a black-yellow mass had been formed, which with the

usual treatment, gave a bright yellow solid melting between 138° and 188° (1.6 g.). This was found to contain 40% of the dibasic and 60% of the monobasic acid.

(ii) The heating was stopped after one hour but the product was still a mixture of 85% dibasic and 15% monobasic acid.

(iii) In this experiment, the heating was continued till complete decarboxylation took place, which was ascertained by periodically examining a portion. The heating was for 2 hours on a water-bath and 6 hours at 110-115°, the product however, contained 30% of the dibasic acid.

Other experiments, one with heating at 113-120° for 10 hours and second with heating at 120-130° for 14 hours, failed to completely decarboxylate the product in the absence of pyridine. And yet the decarboxylation seemed to start within one hour on a water-bath.

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